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CONSERVATION OF NATURAL RESOURCES

Seema Sharma

Department of Political Science, Govt. M.L.B. Girls P.G. College, Indore

ABSTRACT

The importance of natural resources in sustaining productivity and environmental protection is now relatively more realized than the past. Over the past few decades or so, more and more attention is being paid all over the world to conserve the Natural Resources. Natural resources are important material basis for a stable economy and social development too. With Industrialization and Urbanization, mankind's great demand for natural resources and their large scale exploitation and consumption has resulted in the weakening, deterioration and exhaustion of these resources. Human existence depends on the natural resources and the environment and the maintenance of which is now increasingly being considered as essential for mankind. As human populations increase and natural resources become more limited, there is a critical need for trained conservation professionals in natural resources conservation.

Natural Resources are those environmental gifts which satisfy the human wants. They are the means of attaining social objectives. Conservation of natural resources is the wise use of the earth's resources by humanity to achieve its benefits for the longest possible period of time and ensure availability of these resources for the further generation. One difficult task faced by all countries is to guarantee the lasting utilization of natural resources at the lowest possible environmental cost while still assuring economical and social development.

Keywords:

Natural Resources, Sustaining, Conservation, Social Development.

INTRODUCTION

Keeping in mind the present scenario and conditions of natural resource utilization various conservation methods need to be undertaken to ensure a sustainable use of these precious resources.

In most parts of the world, water is a scarce resource. Almost all of the water on Earth, more than 97 percent of it, is seawater in the oceans and the rest is fresh water.

Life is impossible without water resource. Water supports all forms of life including agricultural, human and plant. Water is used for domestic requirements, for raising crops and trees and also needed in manufacturing industries.

There is a necessity to use this valuable exhaustible resource wisely and in a sustainable manner. The goals of water conservation efforts include: ensuring availability of water for future generations, Energy conservation which is proper and efficient use of energy and Habitat conservation which is minimizing human water use that helps to preserve fresh fire habitats for local wildlife and migrating waterfowl, as well as reducing the need to build new dams and other

water division infrastructures. Ensuring proper household, commercial and agriculture applications, slowing down surface run-off to improve underground storage and water harvesting are few preventive steps. Modern methods of irrigation such as Drip irrigation technique and sprinkles method of irrigation should be adopted. Recycled water should be used in industries.

Land is the most fundamental among natural resources on which human existence and prosperity depends. Its particular use and management affects: a) the quantity and quality of the production and employment associated with land both directly and indirectly; b) the degree of pollution/degradation of not only land but also water and air; c) integrity of the biological systems upon which human life depends; d) the preservation of open space; and e) the customs, character and way of life of communities and individuals. Optimum use of this resource ensures continued availability of the basic human needs for food, fiber and shelter and improves the overall environment.

Preventive methods and conservation programs to conserve land and soil have been launched and techniques including terracing, contour farming and crop rotation are practiced in Agriculture to prevent soil erosion. Improving technology has helped preventing unwise exploitation of land and soil.

Forests are an extremely important natural resource that can potentially be sustainably harvested and managed to yield a diversity of commodities of economic importance. Forests provide additional goods and services that are important to both human welfare and to ecological integrity, including the control of erosion and water flows, and the cleansing of air and water of pollutants. Unfortunately, in most cases forests have been unsustainably overharvested, resulting in the exhaustion of the forest_resource and widespread ecological degradation. It is critical that in the future all forest harvesting is conducted in a manner that is more responsible in terms of sustaining the resource.

The preventive methods that can be adopted include a) One of the main reasons of deforestation is commercial felling of trees therefore, cutting should be regulated by adopting methods like Clear cutting, Selective cutting, and Shelter wood cutting. b) Fire suppression techniques like developing three meter wide five lanes around the periphery of the fire, back fires, arrangement of water spray are also in use. C) Fresh afforestation programmes should be started. New plantation would not only increase the forest cover but also help in making up the eco-balance.

The wildlife, which refers to all living organisms in their natural habitat other than cultivated plants and domesticated animals, has great importance in the ecological balance. The birds, animals and other forms of life are very important for ecology. Wildlife maintains ecological 'balance of nature' and maintain food chain and nature cycles.

Many wild plants provide useful substances like timber, paper, gums etc. and they also have wide applications in Ayurveda and other branches of medicine. Wild animal's products are tusk, ivory, leather, honey etc. Destruction to wildlife leads to destruction of ecological balance.

Various steps have been taken and need to be taken to preserve wildlife. Establishment of National parks and Wildlife sanctuaries, Focusing Public attention should be focused on making efforts for preservation of wildlife. Some steps in the direction of wildlife conservation that can be taken are protecting habitat by protecting forests, delimiting the areas of their natural habitat, protecting wildlife from pollution and from natural hazards, imposing complete restriction on hunting and capturing of wildlife and on export and import of wildlife products developing sanctuaries for specific wild animals or for general wildlife and developing general awareness at national and international level regarding protection of wildlife.

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